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Abstract	This document presents the advancements made in the first half of the AD4GD project on leveraging AI and HPC to support AD4GD research with a strong focus on pilot cases. The tasks carried in this work package focused on developing AI-powered tools for analyzing environmental data, predicting future conditions, and designing intuitive user interfaces. Specific AI applications include water level forecasting for Berlin lakes and connectivity map generation for Catalonia region. The integration of these tools with other AD4GD components is also discussed, highlighting their contribution to the overall project goals of promoting FAIR science practices and addressing environmental challenges.
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
c-GAN	conditional Generative Adversarial Network
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FROST	Fraunhofer Opensource SensorThings-Server
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCD	Human-Centered Design
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICT	Integral terrestrial connectivity index
IoT	Internet of Things
LSTM	Long short-term memory
LULC	Land-use land-cover
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
RNN	Recurrent Neural network
SARIMA	Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
UI	User Interface

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D5.1 "AI, ML in HPC and cloud for FAIR Science Services" summarises the progress for the first half of the AD4GD project on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and High Performance Computing (HPC) usage for assisting pilot studies, the design and implementation of User Interfaces (UI), and the integration of such tools with the rest of the work packages. AI has emerged as a powerful tool for addressing environmental challenges; such of those presented in the pilot cases studied in AD4GD, due to its ability to analyze vast datasets, identify complex patterns, and optimize resource allocation. AI algorithms can process and interpret environmental data from satellites and IoT sensors, enabling rapid identification of pollution hotspots, deforestation rates, and climate change impacts. Moreover, AI-powered predictive modelling can forecast future environmental conditions, allowing for proactive measures to mitigate risks and ensure sustainability. The results of applying these tools to cases such as pilot 1 for the determination water level for lakes in Berlin area, and the possible impact of rains on them, or to help providing fast calculation of connectivity maps in the Catalonia region for pilot 2 are presented in this document. It is also worthwhile mentioning that the computational demands of AI applications often need HPC systems, which provide the necessary processing power to handle large-scale datasets and complex algorithms. HPC clusters enable AI models to be trained on massive datasets, improving their accuracy and efficiency in solving problems as the one described. In addition, HPC can accelerate AI-driven simulations and predictions, allowing for more timely and informed decision-making. Likewise, a user-friendly and intuitive interface is crucial for effective decision-making in the context of these pilot studies. Such an interface allows stakeholders and general users, often non-experts in environmental science or technology, to easily accessing and understanding complex data and models. By providing clear visualizations, interactive tools, and intuitive navigation (for example to visualize the complete information in terms of water level, quality and weather for each lake in case of pilot 1) a well-designed UI empowers decision-makers to quickly identify trends, assess risks, and explore potential solutions. This accessibility fosters a more informed and engaged public, ultimately leading to better-informed policy decisions and more effective environmental management strategies. Finally, all these progresses would not be relevant if it is not properly in line with the rest of the work performed in different components of the AD4GD project.

1 INTRODUCTION

This document (Deliverable 5.1 for the AD4GD project) presents the initial results achieved in the context of Tasks 5.1 "*AI and ML for data quality and uncertainty management and ground truthing*", 5.2 "*AI, ML in HPC and cloud for data analytics and knowledge generation*", 5.3 "*User interface definition for intuitive decision making*", 5.4 "*Front-end implementation of AD4GD user applications*" and 5.5 "*Supporting convergence of High Performance Computing, cloud, data and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modelling*" as part of Work Package 5 "*Artificial Intelligence for Data Certainty, Quality and Exploitability*". Current text is aligned with the previous work carried out by other WPs and the technical requirements identified to perform the AD4GD pilots' main targets.

This way, results are presented in three parts directly derived from the mentioned tasks:

- i. First part describes the infrastructure and use of HPC hardware for the specific needs of AI developments. An overview of the architecture designed and implemented is provided, as well as details on the specific tools to do so. The AI models specifically deployed and trained for each pilot case are discussed, with a previous analysis on the data available for each case and how that fits into the models chosen.
- ii. The second part provides a full description of the work done in terms of user interfaces designed, which is done based on the context of use and user requirements per pilot. This section starts by presenting initial prototypes and reaches the description of an actual practical implementation.
- iii. Finally, a section giving details on how different aspects of the Project, such as HPC, cloud, data and AI are put together to get the best out of these resources. This is a section that provides initial insights on the integration of tasks coming from different work packages of the AD4GD project.

The conclusion of this work with further results will be presented on a future deliverable (D5.2).

2 AI IN HPC PLATFORM

As stated in [1], current advances in **AI algorithms and ML/DL technologies require computational potentials and runtimes that go beyond the realm of personal and single-server limited computing**. In this sense, High Performance Computing (HPC) combine distributed and scalable computational resources (servers), network capabilities (accessibility) and software tools (security, management, algorithms design, etc.) to offer a versatile, scalable and customised environment for ML models development, training and deployment. These HPC environments also considers energy efficiency and completely abstract AI engineers from hardware and software management, allowing better allocation of human resources.

AD4GD designs and provides its own HPC infrastructure for WP5 ML models development and inferencing, including cutting-edge DevOps hardware and software technologies to build a MLOps framework that support the AI targets of the project.

2.1 INFRASTRUCTURE

As mentioned, High-Performance Computing (HPC) environments have become key tools for advancing artificial intelligence (AI) research and development. These environments are usually offered as scalable hardware (servers and network resources) clusters, sized according to a set of requirements that are directly linked to the project targets and scope. The HPC cluster must provide the computational power necessary to efficiently support software intended to deploy and train complex machine learning (ML) models, such as neural networks, analyze massive datasets, and develop innovative AI solutions. A well-orchestrated HPC infrastructure is crucial to maximizing the efficiency and scalability of AI workloads. One of AD4GD goals is to make use of this technology to tackle its objectives, in particular for pilot cases where AI solutions are proposed, and that will be conveniently described in the next sections.

2.1.1 HPC CLUSTER (HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE)

AI developments in AD4GD rely on ML models. These are basically mathematical and probabilistic algorithms that require tons of computational iterations. Common consumer hardware (e.g. desktops/laptops) may not be able to support the quick and extensive computations required by models to calculate and update millions of parameters in a run-time for only a single iteration. For these purposes, including ML/DL models development, training and exploitation in production environments, dedicated servers organised in clusters combining computational resources are commonly used. Today, the combination of **Central Processing Units (CPUs)** as generic computational cores with **Graphics Processing Units (GPUs)** as resources specialised in parallel operations is gaining ground due to the performance improvements provided mainly in training stages. However, due to the characteristics of the developments to be carried out (that do not require high training loads and real-time processing), only CPUs are considered in this work. The amount of **Random Access Memory (RAM)** available in the cluster impacts on the volume of datasets that can be managed by the model within a training iteration: simplistically, the larger the available RAM, the larger the dataset to be used for training. This produces more accurate models using less time (as fewer training rounds are required). Finally, the **storage memory** (usually measured in Terabytes-TB in these platforms) sets the capabilities of the cluster to store full datasets for development and training, as well as outcome data, that be later analysed and processed. As these clusters are in turn linked to Big-Data frameworks (as ML/DL models design usually require large amounts of data), the volume of storage memory must be considered to cover the project's needs.

As an initial approach, and considering the scope, ML and data requirements provided by AD4GD partners, as well as its envisioned access and production capabilities, an **HPC cluster** has been provided by PSNC partner with the following main dimensions:

- **140 Virtual CPUs** to distribute among up 12 server instances.
- **272 Gb of RAM.**
- **2 Tb** (expandable) of **HDD** storage capability.
- **4 Public IPs** (for external access to resources' management).

The AD4GD HPC cluster is a cloud computing infrastructure supported by PSNC and offered through its **OpenStack**¹ platform. This platform allows a customised distribution of the assigned hardware

¹ <https://www.openstack.org/>

resources in the form of tailored virtual servers within a virtual intranet. This creates a virtual servers' cluster, which enables the use of different open-source tools to manage the deployment of software and the resources' usage according to the project's needs.

This HPC Cluster is intended to support the deployment of two related software environments: a) an instance of the **AD4GD dataspace**, which supports and enables pilots' data pipelines and data sharing (with other frameworks, such as the GDDS); and b) an **MLOps infrastructure** that exploits (and contributes to) these data pipelines to develop and deploy the ML models for the designed pilots. For these two deployments, and based on the previous experience in similar platforms provided by ATOS, a **Kubernetes**² cluster is built. Kubernetes is an open source container orchestration platform for setting up and managing HPC clusters, widely used to configure environments similar to the AD4GD needs. Considering this, the HPC cluster has been distributed as follows:

- **Intranet/Internet:** manages the access to services and cluster management from outside the cloud, and all the interconnection between virtual nodes
 - AD4GD router: virtualises all the network services to enable intranet and internet traffic. Manages:
 - External IP 1: exposes Bastion bridge server, which manages the access from outside to the virtual servers, for virtual cluster management.
 - External IP 2: exposes the Kubernetes cluster services (Dataspace and MLOps services/tools) to external users.
 - Bastion server: acts as a bridge to control de access to the HPC cluster resources (virtual servers). It is used for some cluster management operations.
- **Kubernetes Cluster:** intended to deploy and support both, the AD4GD dataspace services and the MLOps infrastructure:
 - 4 Worker servers: support the containers' running (AD4GD services).
 - 2 Master servers: control the deployment and resources usage of all the containers (services), those conforming the AD4GD dataspace and the MLOps framework. Two masters are used to back-up the full (Kubernetes) cluster configuration.
- **Data Persistence:** keep persistence of all data required to support both: Kubernetes containers and configuration, including also the configuration of the HPC cluster parameters and all the datasets (data repositories) managed by pilots:
 - Network File System (NFS) server with a dedicated 1TB of storage supports persistence storage with all the cluster datasets.

The final resources distribution is shown in Figure 1. The cluster uses 130 CPUs + 188 Gb of RAM + 1320 Gb of internal storage for running all the services. It reserves 10 CPUs + 8 GB of RAM + 680 Gb of internal storage for future resources redistribution, as services and pilots progress (if needed).

Figure 1: HPC cluster architecture and resources' distribution.

² <https://kubernetes.io/>

2.1.2 MLOPS FRAMEWORK (SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE)

In addition to hardware, the software stack plays a vital role in optimizing AI workloads. The selection of software components, as well as the tools used to deploy and manage them must align with the hardware capabilities and the specific requirements of our AI applications. In terms of AI deployments and ML/DL models' development, ATOS build and MLOps platform on top of the AD4GD HPC cluster provided by PSNC.

A **Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) framework** consists of a set of workflow practices, derived from cutting-edge DevOps and GitOps principles and orchestrated by specialised software tools, which aim to streamline the process of developing, deploying and maintaining ML models. This framework covers three main stages for ML deployment and exploitation:

- **Data Management & Integration:** includes data management and version control capabilities to handle large datasets to be used in model training and deployment. It also supports storing curated datasets coming from AD4GD pilots, for project's data scientists' access and utilization within the platform.
- **ML Model Development:** enables the model design and coding, embedding AI algorithms and techniques. In this stage, tools that facilitate the usage of different programming languages (mainly those specialised in ML) and libraries, as well as the integration with common coding frameworks such as GitHub/GitLab are useful.
- **ML Model Evaluation and Experimentation:** provides tools to monitor the performance of models and measure their KPIs while training. Also allows the modification of model's parameters to evaluate their impact.
- **ML Model Deployment and Inferencing:** once a first validated version of the model is available, this code is packed to be distributed and deployed in the selected exploitation environments (edge devices, cloud servers, part of bigger applications, etc.). Usually, an API is added to the core model to allow inferencing; its usage by supporting input values injection and extraction of resulting outcomes.

The combination of these four stages directly supports the common ML model's lifecycle: 1) input data collection and pre-processing; 2) training the ML/DL model; 3) storing the trained model; 4) sharing and deploying the resulting model; and 5) re-training and updating the model.

The **software architecture** of this MLOps platform is designed for the development and deployment of AD4GD ML models, according to the needs of the corresponding pilots. It relies on the Kubernetes cluster mentioned in the previous section as the underlying infrastructure to provide a robust and scalable foundation to support the described ML lifecycle.

- **Data management** is a cross-cutting layer, shared with the AD4GD dataspace implementation, which provides datasets for the development (training and testing) and exploitation (inference) of ML models. It supports data storage and persistence based on **MinIO**³ as an open source data repository, compliant with the S3 common extended API. This capability allows data scientists to securely store and manage their curated datasets, ensuring data consistency and traceability.
- The **model development** tool is implemented using **Kubeflow**⁴, a powerful toolset specifically designed for ML workflows and Kubernetes clusters. Kubeflow covers model development, experimentation, evaluation, and monitoring during training, supporting the entire model development process. It integrates with Jupyter Notebooks⁵ and GitHub for models' design and coding.
- **MLFlow**⁶ component facilitates model versioning, reproducibility and distribution, allowing upload and share models and artifacts and implementing the **models' evaluation and experimentation**.
- For **models' deployment and sharing**, the platform uses **Docker** containers to manage and share models' images. This is done using **KServe**⁷ (also a Kubernetes-based tool) making

³ <https://min.io/>

⁴ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

⁵ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁶ <https://mlflow.org/>

⁷ <https://kserve.github.io/website/0.10/>

them readily available for real-time inference. This approach ensures scalability and reliability for serving models in a production environment. Monitoring tools, such as Prometheus + Grafana pair, are also deployed as components in the Kubernetes cluster, enabling continuous monitoring of models (and software) performance and drift detection.

Figure 2: AD4GD MLOps software architecture.

This MLOps architecture ensures continuous evolution in the integration of ML models in software development. Using MLOps techniques, developers keep models accurate and up-to-date by automating their training loops. This includes continuous monitoring, training and deployment processes, allowing models to adapt to changing data and keep performance over time.

In turn, Kubernetes environment offers several advantages, including:

- **Scalability:** Allows for dynamic scaling of resources to meet fluctuating workloads, ensuring optimal utilization of hardware.
- **Portability:** Enables the deployment of AI applications across different hardware environments, providing flexibility and portability.
- **Efficiency:** Simplifies resource management and scheduling, reducing overhead and improving performance.
- **Reliability:** Provides built-in fault tolerance and self-healing mechanisms to ensure high availability and minimize downtime.

The specific components of the MLOps platform are detailed in section 2.3

2.2 DATA MANAGEMENT LAYER

For any AI development, the more data it is available, to achieve an efficient and effective outcome: the larger and more reliable the datasets are used, the more accurate the result will be. AD4GD gathers and processes several datasets to homogenise, harmonise, exploit and expose them, creating its AD4GD dataspace.

For data exploitation and AI development, all these datasets are managed within the Data Management (and integration) layer shown in Figure 2. Datasets resulting from the processes carried out by other AD4GD components are stored and shared internally within the MLOps data repository. These are consumed by

the ML models during their corresponding lifecycles, and, in turn, the models' outcomes also feed the repository as enhanced information.

2.2.1 DATA SOURCES (DATA GATHERING)

This section directly links the AI developments to be carried out within WP5 with the other components of the AD4GD dataspace through the data collected from real infrastructures and processed to be exploited by the AD4GD ML models. It depicts the components that support this data gathering process, including:

IoT FROST Server (WP3)

Different sources of IoT data were selected based on the needs and requirements elaborated by the three AD4GD pilots. In Berlin, the water level, temperature, oxygen and quality are collected through IoT sensors. They are available through the Berlin Wasserportal⁸ in CSV files. To facilitate the utilisation and the analysis of the water data, the information contained in CSV files is converted to be compliant with the OGC SensorThings API plus. Then, the different sorts of data are sent to the FROST server located in the IoT Lab research infrastructure in Geneva.

The second pilot is located in the region of Catalonia and requires calculating the terrestrial connectivity in different habitats. In this context, camera traps are used as IoT sensors to determine the position of wild animals. Species recognition is undertaken after the reception of the images taken by the camera traps and the results are pushed to the FROST server through the OGC SensorThings plus API.

Finally, the third pilot is investigating the potential utilisation of IoT low cost sensors to measure air quality. Existing measurement networks like Sensor.Community⁹ and PurpleAir¹⁰ were studied, in particular the measurements of particulate matter concentrations PM10 and PM2.5. The data quality was examined to detect erroneous measurements. AI/ML tools, can also be used to filter the wrong data. In the end, it is expected to obtain high-resolution maps of pollution levels.

More details can be found in the deliverable D3.1 "Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration Model" [2].

Data Harmonisation tool - Semantic uplift (WP1)

AD4GD pilots, and similar scenarios outside the project, manage different data sources in many different formats and structures, depending on the usually heterogeneous information systems deployed even if represent similar information. All these information models must be homogenised before they can be shared, so that they can be compared and exploited at the same level or for the same purpose. For this target, WP1 developed the AD4GD Green Deal Information Model (GDIM) [3] as a common vocabulary, which defines the data elements, including concepts, properties and relationships relevant to the European Green Deal applications, as well as their associated semantics/meaning for information exchange. This sets the basis of a common GDDS and enables interoperability of different systems. The data harmonisation tool applies these semantic rules to legacy/raw datasets available in pilots' scenarios to obtain homogenised information ready to be shared: a) through its OGC REST API, so can be used for real time inferencing; and b) injected into the AD4GD internal repository to feed ML models development.

Other sources (Pilots' raw data)

AD4GD Pilots have their own proprietary (and legacy) infrastructures to collect their corresponding environmental datasets. In addition, there also exist several open data sources, such as the European Data Portal¹¹, that potentially provide extended information related to pilots. These sources are analysed by pilots' managers and some are directly uploaded in the AD4GD cluster tagged as "Raw Data". These datasets are later processed by the data harmonization tool to feed the models' training. Further descriptions of these datasets are provided in Section 3 of this document.

2.2.2 DATA STORAGE: MINIO STACK

The data management layer (Fig. 2.2) and the AD4GD data repository are based on a MinIO instance. **MinIO** is an open-source (under GNU AGPLv3 license) high performance and distributed object storage system that implements a versatile solution for a wide-range data repository within a MLOps platform. MinIO supports datasets in multiple file formats, such as CSV, JSON, TXT, etc., as well as image files in TIFF, PNG,

⁸ <https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php>

⁹ <https://sensor.community>

¹⁰ <https://openaq.org/>

¹¹ <https://data.europa.eu/en>

JPEG, etc. It has an **intuitive user interface (UI)** that allows users to easily upload datasets via drag-and-drop for all required purposes, as depicted in Figure 3, and provides an **S3 compliant REST API** to support interaction between different software pieces. This API provides a powerful way to enhance efficiency and enable automated post-processed data ingestion and it is used for data exchange with other Work Packages (e.g. WP1 and WP3) as described in Deliverable D4.2.

AD4GD MinIO instance integrates with **Keycloak**. Keycloak¹² is an open-source identity and access management solution that supports **OAuth 2.0**¹³ as the industry-standard protocol for authorization. Using OAuth 2.0 MinIO provides AD4GD users with personal credentials for both: web UI and S3 API accesses, along with the permission to storage buckets per pilot. In addition, users can also create custom buckets to store and manage datasets in case of needed for experimentation.

As an add-on, AD4GD repository instance integrates MinIO with an MQTT broker (Eclipse Mosquitto¹⁴). This open-source broker enables the pipelines' setup, implementing an MQTT notifications system which automatically notifies registered components when new datasets are available in the AD4GD repository and trigger specific actions in those components.

Figure 3: Minio UI instance for AD4GD.

2.3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COMPONENTS

As described in section 2.1 (Figure 1 and Figure 2), the AD4GD cluster provided by PSNC in Poland was set up by ATOS to use Kubernetes to build the AD4GD cluster. This container orchestrator provides the foundations to deploy a complete AI platform along with its corresponding MLOps tools, i.e. all the components that facilitate the deployment and maintenance of ML models in production reliably and efficiently. These components can be seen in Figure 4. This figure relates the MLOps architecture presented in section 2.1.2 with the ML/DL model lifecycle, identifying the core components for each step. This section focuses on the software components specifically intended for AI and ML/DL models' design, development and deployment, including also the tools for the models' distribution and sharing.

Next subsections expand the AD4GD MLOps architecture, describing individually the components selected for its implementation. This selection is based on the previous experience of ATOS in deploying and supporting MLOps frameworks for current EC projects such as EMERALDS¹⁵ or ALCHIMIA¹⁶. In turn, instantiated software tools are open-source components widespread in the AI developer community. This way, its learning curve was very fast within AD4GD.

¹² <https://www.keycloak.org/>

¹³ <https://oauth.net/2/>

¹⁴ <https://mosquitto.org/>

¹⁵ <https://emeralds-horizon.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://alchimia-project.eu/>

Figure 4: AD4GD MLOps – ML model lifecycle implementation.

ML/DL Model development comprises a set of steps to get a first evaluable version of the desired model: i) **data exploration** that preprocesses and analyses the input data identifying the attributes (inputs and outputs), data types and features that assist on the procedures and algorithms to use in the model building. It also includes the labelling of the data (poor, fair, good, etc.) and its conversion into data types that can be understood by ML algorithms; ii) **model building** selects the type of models and algorithms to be evaluated. Depending on the available datasets (labelled/unlabelled), different approaches can be selected. This step evaluates different options using training and testing datasets to select the best approaches, by measuring their performance; iii) **model hyperparameters tuning** goes deeper in the selected model approaches by modifying their algorithm variables (hyperparameters) till the model performance reach around 80%-85%; and finally, iv) **model selection with optimum performance** choose the best one among the pre-selected approaches.

While many software tools exist to support model development, one of the most common solutions widely adopted by the AI developer community is **Jupyter Notebooks**. This is a flexible web tool that facilitates the use of most relevant ML development frameworks, as well as their combination and integration with the rest of the MLOps modules.

AD4GD MLOps offers a Jupyter Notebook environment deployed on Kubernetes cluster, that enables the creation of containers with the developments. Current instance of this Jupyter environment is pre-configured to support common AI libraries, such as **XGBoost**, **PyTorch**, **TensorFlow**, and **Scikit-Learn**, as ML frameworks, plus some other libraries useful to operate within the AD4GD environment such as DVC and MinIO. In addition, **SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP)**¹⁷ library set is added to support Explainable AI (XAI) feature, as one of the current EU requirements in terms of AI developments.

The Jupyter Notebook deployments are supported by **Kubeflow**. This is a MLOps framework which covers most of the models' development stages, including Jupyter Notebooks for models' design and running (performance analysis), automated hyperparameter tuning and model deployment. Kubeflow allows users to create their own containerized Jupyter Notebooks on demand with all necessary Python libraries pre-installed based on developer needs. AD4GD Kubeflow is accessible to project developers, offering a user friendly interface to work with their Jupyter Notebooks.

Finally, the Jupyter Notebooks support direct **integration with GitHub**. This allows AI developers within AD4GD to use the AD4GD GitHub repository to create, develop and share their prototype models (as notebooks), and then run (and test) them directly within the AD4GD MLOps platform.

Figure 5 shows the Kubeflow Web User Interface deployed in the AD4GD MLOps platform, including some of the ML pipelines currently under development for a given AI developer within AD4GD. This user can access (via Web) to its interface to manage his/her ML lifecycles.

¹⁷ <https://shap.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 5: AD4GD Kubeflow UI instance

2.3.1 MLFLOW (MODEL EVALUATION AND EXPERIMENTATION)

Jupyter Notebooks (pre-configured with an initial set of AI libraries) has been defined as the main tool for ML models’ development and Kubeflow as the tool for tracking the models’ lifecycle stages. MLFlow enables the monitoring of the designed models’ performance, including the manipulation of their internal variables (hyperparameters) to optimize them.

MLFlow is a well-known tool within the MLOps community, which includes modules that speed up developer tasks such as experiment tracking and model. These experiments can be managed through its user-friendly interface, which integrates perfectly within the Kubernetes cluster and the Kubeflow environment. Each AD4GD AI developer manages its own dedicated instance of MLFlow server, seamlessly integrated with his/her Jupyter Notebooks (developing models) and the full models’ lifecycle tracking. Using this owned instance allows the AI developer to run its models with different configurations and embedded algorithms to obtain optimized versions for real-world evaluations. In turn, this setup provides a centralized approach for documenting model experiments and managing models within the AD4GD MLOps platform.

Figure 6: AD4GD MLFlow capture.

2.3.2 KSERVE (MODEL DEPLOYMENT)

After experimentation stage, models' versions for inferencing can be deployed and shared through the AD4GD MLOps platform. The models' deployment is configured to be automated, using Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines configured through GitHub Actions¹⁸. These pipelines simplify the deployment process: once an AD4GD user has developed and registered their model (Jupyter + MLFlow + Kubeflow), deployment is initiated by simply pushing code to the designated AD4GD repository. This action triggers a CI/CD pipeline that automatically pulls the trained model, packages the model and deploys it within a Kubernetes environment, removing any complexity of Kubernetes-based deployment from developers. The resulting models' code is packed using Docker¹⁹ containers which facilitates its standard distribution mechanisms.

For this models' handling process (models' deployment and sharing), **Kserve** was integrated into the platform. Kserve is a tool that automates and simplifies model deployment in Kubernetes environments. Kserve is also deployed along Kubeflow. This way, models are ready for inferences and hosted in the MLOps platform, leveraging Kubernetes robustness and scalability.

¹⁸ <https://docs.github.com/en/actions>

¹⁹ <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>

3 DATA QUALITY AND UNCERTAINTY MANAGEMENT

In the context of projects where the nature of data varies not only in terms of sources but also on its nature, it is of utter importance to guarantee the quality of the data to be used, as well as to keep a consistency among different sources. There are many cases in which available datasets provide information that was not checked before, being available to be consumed. Possible sources of low quality data include missing data, incongruent values (e.g. negative values for precipitations) or wrong measurement units.

It is also likely that data coming from different sources do not share the same time resolution and/or timestamps. The first case would be that there might be data that is gathered on a daily basis and another on an hourly basis, for example. It is also possible for data with the same time resolution to not share timestamps. There is also the possibility of having data that does not have a consistency on the periodicity of its samples. An example of this can be seen in Figure 7. Even though these scenarios are not strictly errors, these lack of synchronicity needs to be managed before using the data as input to a ML model to correctly provide an inferred output.

In order to solve all these possible causes of low quality, the data coming from different sources is resampled and interpolated to unified timestamps in order to mash it up. An example result of selecting some data (columns), interpolating and resampling can be seen in Figure 8.

	datetime	water temperature	conductivity	depth	pH value	turbidity	chlorophyll a	phycocyanin	oxygen saturation	oxygen concentration	battery
0	2007-07-20 16:09:58	23.91	663.0	0.25	8.98	22.60	6.1	7.0	198.30	16.70	12.3
1	2007-07-20 16:49:58	23.71	667.5	1.43	8.96	27.45	5.2	4.8	198.30	16.70	12.3
2	2007-07-20 16:54:58	23.82	661.0	1.43	8.97	27.50	4.9	4.5	201.20	16.96	12.3
3	2007-07-20 16:59:59	23.82	659.0	1.43	8.96	11.05	8.2	8.5	203.80	17.19	12.3
4	2007-07-20 17:19:57	23.76	678.0	1.44	8.98	11.40	8.1	8.9	204.25	17.24	12.5
⋮											
313710	2012-12-08 09:00:00	1.89	902.70	1.49	8.50	-0.15	5.89	0.31	85.35	12.17	12.51
313711	2012-12-08 09:05:00	1.82	902.62	1.49	8.50	-0.03	5.97	0.29	85.57	12.22	12.51
313712	2012-12-08 09:10:00	1.79	902.86	1.49	8.50	-0.10	5.98	0.28	85.71	12.26	12.51

Figure 7: Example of data with insistent periodicity in the samples timestamp, in this particular case is data for Müggelsee lake obtained from FRED (Freshwater Research and Environmental Database).

	datetime	temperature_2m	precipitation	pressure_msl
0	2007-07-21 00:00:00	19.5	1.1	1013.8
1	2007-07-21 01:00:00	19.0	0.0	1013.9
2	2007-07-21 02:00:00	18.5	0.0	1014.3
3	2007-07-21 03:00:00	18.4	0.0	1014.8
4	2007-07-21 04:00:00	18.1	0.0	1015.2

Figure 8: Example of data already pre-processed to solve issues presented in Figure 7.

3.1 KNOWLEDGE GENERATION

3.1.1 PILOT 1: WATER AVAILABILITY/QUALITY

Berlin's ecosystems are under pressure from rapid urbanization and climate change. Despite covering 30% of the city, Berlin's forests, green spaces, and water bodies face challenges. 6% of Berlin is covered by water and includes the Spree-Havel river and lake system, as well as over 300 small urban lakes. These lakes suffer from extreme temperatures and rainfall, but also offer valuable biodiversity and recreational opportunities. Small lakes under 50 hectares fall outside the scope of the EU Water Framework Directive's

monitoring and action plans, receiving attention only in specific cases, such as when they serve as bathing areas.

Water availability is a major issue for lakes in the Berlin area, as they serve as vital ecosystems, providing habitat for diverse aquatic life, filtering pollutants from the water, and contributing to the city's overall environmental health. They also offer recreational opportunities for residents and visitors. Insufficient water levels can lead to decreased biodiversity, reduced water quality, among other issues. Moreover, the lakes play a crucial role in mitigating the effects of climate change by regulating local temperatures and absorbing rainwater, helping to prevent flooding. All these aspects directly affect the quality of life for Berlin's population. Water scarcity significantly impacts the recreational, provisioning, and cooling services provided by urban lakes, and is strongly influenced by environmental factors like precipitation. Understanding water availability trends is crucial, especially given their greater seasonal and weather dependence. By analyzing long-term water availability trends for individual lakes and comparing multiple lakes simultaneously, we can better prioritize conservation efforts and identify which lakes are most vulnerable to drying up during periods of drought.

3.1.1.1 AI MODEL PIPELINE

Pilot 1 develops an AI prediction model (described in the next section) that has a configurable pre-scheduled run (e.g. every hour or every time a new input becomes available). This model is implemented and deployed according to the ML lifecycle defined in Figure 4, but its step 4 (model inference) will be triggered automatically, fed by new data uploaded to the internal AD4GD repository and providing its results also to this repository. These predictions (model results) are served asynchronously (on demand) and/or synchronously (via MQTT notifications) through the REST S3 API supported by the internal repository.

Figure 9: Pilot 1 ML Model's inferencing schema.

As shown in Figure 9, Pilot 1 prediction model will be run when a new harmonised dataset related to this pilot is uploaded by the AD4GD semantic adaptor. MQTT implemented notifications can be used to trigger the model. The prediction results are stored in the MinIO internal repository. The Frontend component can query/retrieve these new predictions through the exposed S3 API, synchronously every e.g. 1 hour or asynchronously, after receiving an MQTT notification. The final integration and consuming implementations will be provided in D5.2.

3.1.1.2 USE CASE PERFORMANCE

In order to facilitate Berlin's authorities' decision making by having more and better information on their lakes, we intend to use AI models to produce results that are relevant in terms of water availability. The approach proposed uses historical data both on lakes' water level as well as weather data, such as (but not

limited to) precipitation. The first goal would be to obtain a model to predict the future behaviour of lakes based on those historical data. The data gathered for this purpose was taken from two different sources: the water level was obtained from Wasserportal Berlin²⁰, where other relevant variables such as ground water level can be found as well; and weather data collected from Open-Meteo²¹. An example of the combination of these data after the preprocessing described in section 2.2, to guarantee data quality and uncertainty management, can be seen in Figure 9. There, it can be noticed that initially only historical data is stored in a buffer, then as predictions are made, those predictions are sent to the buffer to compute new ones. The idea is to use a sliding window on old data and new produced data as an input to the predictor. A schema describing this is shown in Figure 10 for a generic predictor block.

The predictor itself can be implemented using different approaches. Given that the problem presented can be described as the forecasting of a time series, the most straightforward AI approach would be using a model called ARIMA (*AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average*). From its name, *AutoRegressive* means that it regresses on its own prior values. *Integrated* means that the model observes the difference between static data values and previous ones, in order to achieve stationary data that is not subject to seasonality. Finally, *Moving Average* represents the dependency between an observed value and the residual error from a moving average model applied to previous observations. Even though this model has been a standard for forecasting in statistics for ages, there are certain assumptions in it, such as the seasonality that might be too difficult to fulfil. There are seasonal versions of this model (SARIMA) that intend to tackle this particular aspect; however, the results did not perform as well as expected.

To solve this issue, a more involved model was chosen that implies the use of a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), a class of artificial neural networks for sequential data processing. The predictor was then implemented using a model called long-short-term memory (LSTM). The intuition behind the LSTM architecture is to create an additional module in a neural network that learns when to remember and when to forget pertinent information. In other words, the network effectively learns which information might be needed later on in a sequence and when that information is no longer needed. A detail on actual LSTM architecture used can be seen in Figure 11. The result for the forecasted water level for lake Plötzensee can be seen in Figure 12, where we can visualize in blue the actual values for the water level, in orange the result of the model on the data on which it was trained matching the dynamics, and finally in green the recursive forecasted values for the water level using that same model. It is important to remark that we did our predictions for dates for which we already had ground truth data to be able to determine if the model was working properly, but that was data that was never seen by the model during training.

Being able to obtain the future values for the water level in different lakes in Berlin already adds value to the data available and gives an insight on the near future that can be of help for decision making. However, we also want to somehow use this information to classify the lakes based on the potential impact of precipitation on their water level, i.e. what could happen to them in case of massive rains or absence of them. To do so, we need to understand not only the relation between water level and precipitation, but also how the dynamics of the water levels behave for all lakes. To this end two analysis were performed on the data available for a selected group of 18 lakes (these lakes were selected by the pilot leader, i.e. KWB), which are:

- Flughafensee
- Plötzensee
- Schäfersee
- Malchower See
- Weißer See
- Orankesee
- Obersee
- Fennpfuhl
- Biesdorfer Baggersee
- Fennsee
- Lietzensee

²⁰ <https://wasserportal.berlin.de/>

²¹ <https://open-meteo.com/>

- Halensee
- Dianasee
- Hundekehlesee
- Großglienicker See
- Grunewaldsee
- Dreipfuhl
- Waldsee Zehlendorf

The first analysis on this subset of Berlin lakes consisted of clustering them based solely on the dynamics of the water level time series. To this end, and to avoid the analysis on absolute values, which provide useful information in other areas, but not regarding the dynamics, we first normalized the water level data. That is, we made the signals so that they go from 0 to 1 normalized using the maximum value from all lakes. Once this step is done, we used the k-means clustering method that aims to partition n observations into k clusters in which each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean (cluster centers or cluster centroid), serving as a prototype of the cluster. The result of this clustering can be seen in Figure 13. Given this clustering uses only water level information, it would be nice to know if there is any relationship between the classification obtained, and the precipitations. To this end, we performed a more involved analysis correlating the water level time series with the precipitation in the Berlin area. The results can be seen in Figure 14. We can see that the results are almost identical, in the sense we can identify similar clusters of lakes based on the correlation calculated. This gives us the confirmation that the approach followed in the previous analysis (i.e. k-means clustering of water level signals), that can easily be calculated on demand, giving a good indication on the impact of precipitation on the dynamics of each lake. The idea would be to ultimately combine the results from this clustering and the forecasted values to see how precipitation impacts on future behaviour of Berlin lakes. Such analysis is still a work in progress and will be presented in detail in future deliverables.

	waterLevel	meanPrecipitations
datetime		
2015-11-01	124	1.281918
2015-11-02	121	1.281644
2015-11-03	121	1.281644
2015-11-04	121	1.281644
2015-11-05	120	1.282192
2015-11-06	121	1.286849
2015-11-07	121	1.287397
2015-11-08	121	1.289315
2015-11-09	121	1.289589
2015-11-10	121	1.291233

Figure 10: Actual data being used as an input for modelling.

Figure 11: Predictor schema.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm_1 (LSTM)	(None, 64)	17,152
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 32)	2,080
dense_4 (Dense)	(None, 16)	528
dense_5 (Dense)	(None, 2)	34

Figure 12: Detail on architecture used for predictor, based on the use of an LSTM. This particular model has 19,794 parameters to be trained, and presents a final dense layer of shape 2, given that it predicts both precipitation and water level.

Figure 13: Result of the forecasted water level for Plötzensee lake using the LSTM proposed.

Figure 14: Clustering results for a subset of Berlin lakes, where the number of cluster k was set to 3. In each subplot we can see the dynamics for all the lakes belonging to each one of the three clusters.

Figure 15: Correlation values of water level and precipitations, where we coloured and grouped the lakes based on these values, obtaining similar results of those presented in Figure 13.

3.1.2 PILOT 2: BIODIVERSITY

Biodiversity conservation and ecological connectivity are increasingly recognized as critical global and European policy priorities. Functional Landscape Connectivity (FLC), which measures the ability of species to move through landscapes, is a key factor in maintaining biodiversity. Governments at various levels are seeking standardized metrics to assess the state and protection of biodiversity for international reporting. However, there is also a need for accessible information products that are sensitive to local contexts to facilitate dialogue with stakeholders. Pilot 2 focuses on the Catalonia (region in Spain) as a case study. It explores different approaches to quantifying connectivity, including graph-based models and remote sensing methods. These methods aim to provide a better understanding of FLC and inform policy decisions related to protected areas, land use planning, and agricultural practices.

3.1.2.1 AI MODEL PIPELINE

Pilot 2 provides an AI inferencing ML model (described in the next section) which works “on demand”. Pilot’s 2 data sources are harmonised and uploaded into the AD4GD main repository to create a large historical dataset used to develop, train and test the pilot’s model (steps 1 and 2 of the ML lifecycle shown in Figure 4). Once created, it is stored (step 3 of its lifecycle) and, unlike pilot’s 1 model, this one is exposed through a REST API to be called every time a new iteration is required by the end user. In this case (Figure 16) when the AD4GD Frontend component requires a new inference, it queries the model’s API providing an input vector which includes all values (initial conditions) needed to launch the model’s algorithms. When the model finalises, it returns an output vector with the results of the inference to the Frontend, which will format and present this result to the final user. The final implementation and execution of the model will be described in D5.2.

Figure 16: Pilot 2 “on demand” ML Model’s inferencing schema.

3.1.2.2 USE CASE PERFORMANCE

Two frameworks to assess habitat connectivity will be evaluated and compared in this pilot:

- Integral terrestrial connectivity index (ICT) computed through MiraMon software (Marulli and Mallarach 2005).
- Indices based on graph theory and computed mostly via Graphab (Foltête et al., 2021) or Conefor (Saura and Torné, 2009) software.

In the context of this Work Package we study an AI based alternative to the calculation of different ICT that are performed using the Land-Use Land-Cover (LULC) maps pixel-wise. That is, for each pixel in the input map (LULC), a calculation is done in the neighbourhood of that pixel to compute the output value (ICT). This approach implies the use of nested iteration loops that translate into high computational costs and long calculations times.

If we were to evaluate the implications of introducing a modification in the landscape, e.g. building a highway in a forest area, we would need to reevaluate the results for each explored setup of the highway. This kind of experiment could provide helpful information for decision making. If the possible scenarios that we want to evaluate are numerous, the time consumed to evaluate each of them would make this kind of unviable. One alternative approach to make these studies possible and reduce computational costs would be the use of AI to compute ICT values based on LULC maps. The idea behind this is replacing the exact calculation of those pixel-wise metrics by the approximation provided by inferencing on an AI model.

The first thing to evaluate when selecting a model is understanding the inputs and outputs the model needs to handle. As mentioned, the input would be a LULC map, an example of this map can be seen in Figure 15. In this kind of map, each pixel is associated with one of 8 classes:

- 0 = No data
- 1 = Aquatic environment
- 2 = Urban
- 3 = Herbaceous crops
- 4 = Woody crops
- 5 = Shrublands
- 6 = Forest
- 7 = Bare soil

The size of these maps is 8651x8981 pixels. On the other hand, the resolution of ICT output maps can be selected to a desired value. For our case we want to obtain the same size as the input. Each pixel in these kinds of maps take a value in the range $[0, 2.5]$, an example for ICT_Forest can be seen in Figure 16. The first thing that should be noted is that images this size are difficult to process as is, so it would be convenient to divide them into tiles that result more manageable to a ML model. The result of dividing both input and output maps can be seen in Figure 17.

Having cleared what are inputs and outputs, we are able to build a model and train it so that we can obtain an approximation (a prediction) of the output based on the input. A model that suits the specific needs is the network called Pix2Pix, a conditional image-to-image translation architecture that uses a conditional generative adversarial network (c-GAN) objective combined with a reconstruction loss. A more general a thorough explanation on how this network works can be found in TensorFlow documentation²². Some initial results on the predicted output and how it compares to the actual calculated results can be seen in Figure 18. Ultimately, these predicted tiles could be put back together to build the complete output map or used as parts according to the particular needs of the problem to be studied.

Figure 17: Land-use land-cover example for Catalonia area corresponding to 1987.

²² <https://www.tensorflow.org/tutorials/generative/pix2pix>

Calculated ICT_Forest for Catalonia area (1987)

Figure 18: Calculated ICT_Forest for Catalonia area corresponding to 1987.

Figure 19: Input (left) and output (right) maps sliced into smaller images that are easier to handle using a ML model.

Figure 20: Example initial results obtained using Pix2pix network using slices of LUCL map as an input, and a comparison to ground-truth ICT_Forest analytical calculations.

3.2 FUTURE WORK

The work described in the previous sections is not considered to provide final results yet. Further developments are needed in both pilots to achieve the goals described. In particular, for pilot 1 we intend to provide the combination of the results from clustering and the forecasted values to evaluate the impact of precipitation on future behaviour of Berlin lakes. Further improvements on the models performance is expected in the next deliverable. It would be helpful to produce some sort of ranking of lakes to indicate stakeholders which are the ones that present a higher impact, and hence are more important to take action sooner. It is

also important to mention that so far, harmonized data coming from WP1 is not available yet, but it is key to this project, as it would simplify the pre-processing step needed to develop ML models. For this reason, results for a single lake are presented, as it would not make much of a sense to train models for all available lakes and then retrain them once the harmonized data is available. However, the process of training new models for other lakes will be straightforward once the complete pipeline for a single lake is completed.

As for pilot 2, only initial results were presented and further training and improvements are expected in the next period.

4 USER INTERFACES

4.1 DESIGN OF USER INTERFACES

For the design of the user interfaces in AD4GD, we are following the Human-Centered Design (HCD) approach according to ISO 9241-210 (International Organization for Standardization 2019 [6]), complemented by Co-Design methods in order to build meaningful digital solutions for the GDSS.

The Human-Centered Design process consists of four steps: (1) understanding and specifying the context of use, (2) specifying the user requirements, (3) producing design solutions, and (4) evaluating the design, as detailed in Deliverable 1.1 [7] (D1.1 Fig.1). This deliverable specifically reports on the third step, producing design solutions, for Pilot 1 (SplashBoard), Pilot 2 (BioConnect), and the General User Interface.

Throughout the design process, we followed an iterative design approach. This approach involves continuously refining our prototype design by evaluating it with relevant stakeholders, updating user requirements, and incorporating their needs into the design.

Figure 21: HCD design process model for designing solutions.

Figure 19 outlines the aimed design process for the tools to be developed. The process includes two iteration cycles before reaching the design freeze stage. Each iteration cycle involves evaluating the current design solution with relevant stakeholders, updating the user requirements based on their feedback, and implementing new or revised design solutions to the user interface to meet the collected requirements. The following sections provide a detailed explanation of the creation of each version of the prototypes for each tool.

4.1.1 PROTOTYPE VERSION 1

In the first step of the defined design process, paper prototypes were created by using the Design Study Method²³, a collaborative design approach that facilitates quick development of creative ideas and design solutions. During this process, team members individually sketch ideas, then present and discuss them together. This method fosters creativity, encourages all team members to contribute their perspectives, and helps teams to quickly converge on design solutions. Starting with a pen-and-paper prototype has the advantage of engaging every team member, being very cost-effective, and requiring minimal time.

The created paper prototypes were then converted into simple low fidelity wireframes using Figma (see Figure 20, Figure 21 and Figure 22). At this early stage of the design process, creating a highly functional prototype was not necessary for gathering feedback. Instead, the focus was on the basic layout, structure, and primary functions of the tools to get a first common overall understanding of the working results in the process so far.

²³ <https://minchen.medium.com/what-is-design-studio-method-f52ba077a52e>

Figure 22: Excerpt Paper Prototype (left) and low fidelity wireframe (right) - SplashBoard – Tool.

Figure 23: Excerpt Paper Prototype (left) and low fidelity wireframe (right) - BioConnect Tool.

Figure 24: Excerpt Paper Prototype (left) and low fidelity wireframe (right) - General User Interface.

4.1.2 PROTOTYPE VERSION 2

The low-fidelity wireframes in Figma were then run through the first iteration cycle, beginning with an evaluation. During the evaluation, the relevant pilot partners reviewed the low-fidelity wireframes of the tools applicable to them and answered some general questions regarding the to-be-developed tool. Their feedback was collected and compared against the existing user requirements (see D1.1). In cases where discrepancies were identified, the user requirements were adjusted and/or new ones were created. Subsequently, the wireframes were updated into low-fidelity prototypes (Version 2).

In creating low-fidelity prototypes, visual styling aspects for guidance and orientation were deliberately overlooked, with the focus being on the functionality of the tools and the development of effective user flows.

Figure 25: Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) Splashboard – Tool.

Figure 26: Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) - BioConnect – Tool.

Figure 27: Excerpt Low-Fidelity Prototype (Version 2) - General User Interface.

4.1.3 PROTOTYPE VERSION 3

The low fidelity prototypes then served as a foundation for the second iteration cycle. In this cycle, the tools were evaluated by potential end-users who are not partners in the AD4GD project. The feedback of the end users is then used to further advance the prototype based on the newly defined or adapted user requirements. Version 3 of the prototype is a high fidelity prototype, meaning visual aspects are also included. For that purpose a design system was developed.

A design system is a collection of standards, guidelines, and components that provides a structured approach to designing and building digital solutions. Using a design system ensures visual consistency across products, efficiency, as pre-made UI components and elements can be used over and over again, and cohesion in the design and development process²⁴.

Currently, we are at different stages of the design process for each tool. Therefore, the current status of each tool (Pilot 1, Pilot 2, GenUI) will be described independently in the following section.

4.1.3.1 PILOT 1 - SPLASHBOARD

The low-fidelity prototype (Version 2) was evaluated by three district office employees in Berlin who are responsible for decision-making concerning actions related to small urban lakes in the city. These employees are part of the previous defined end-user group. Their input and feedback on the tool were used to refine the design and develop a high-fidelity prototype (Version 3) (see Figure 26).

Figure 28: Excerpt High-Fidelity Prototype (Version 3) Splashboard – Tool.

The high-fidelity prototype was reviewed by the pilot partner, who had also participated in the evaluation of the initial design, the low-fidelity wireframes. Minor adjustments were made to the high-fidelity prototype based on that feedback.

The Splashboard for Pilot 1 has now reached the Design Freeze stage, marking the completion of the design process (see Figure 27). The tool is currently undergoing technical development and implementation.

Figure 29: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - Pilot 1.

The data to be displayed in this UI will be gathered from the MinIO instance. Not only historical data will be stored in it, but also AI enriched data as described in section 3.1.1.1. That means that the data to be displayed per lake is expected to be automatically updated either periodically or as soon as new data is available respecting the forecasted values for water level. The way the lake classification based on the

²⁴ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/design-systems-101/>

impact of precipitations is going to be consumed from the AI system is yet to determine, and further developments are expected to be presented in the next deliverable.

4.1.3.2 PILOT 2 - BIOCONNECT TOOL

For Pilot 2, the current status of the design is the low-fidelity prototype (Version 2) (see Figure 28). We are currently in the process of scheduling evaluations with potential end users, public servants involved in decision-making regarding land use changes in Barcelona. Due to their busy schedules, it has been challenging to secure suitable time slots for the evaluation of the tool. However, these evaluations are planned for September and October 2024.

The feedback gathered from these evaluations will be utilised to develop the high-fidelity prototype (Version 3). Since the design system has already been established, creating the high-fidelity prototype will be less time consuming compared to starting from scratch.

Once the high-fidelity prototype is created, the pilot partners who participated in the initial evaluation of the low fidelity wireframes will be invited to review the high-fidelity prototype and provide their feedback. Following this, the design will reach the Design Freeze stage, after which the tool will proceed to technical implementation. The high-fidelity prototype will serve as a template for this phase.

Figure 30: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - Pilot 2.

For this pilot it is planned to provide a way to interact with the AI described in the previously by creating artificial changes in connectivity maps, as shown in Figure 24, where the "+ Create scenario" allows the end user to do so. Once that modified map is ready, the model described in section 3.1.2 will be used as an input for inference resulting in an on-demand updated map. This process was described in section 3.1.2.1 from the MLops perspective.

4.1.3.3 GENERAL USER INTERFACE

For the AD4GD data space general user interface, it was decided that it will not be technically implemented. Instead, a prototype proposal will be provided. As a result, the evaluation with potential end users was skipped, and the low-fidelity prototype was evaluated and reviewed by the AD4GD project coordinator instead. (see Figure 29).

Figure 31: Current state HCD process model for designing solutions - General User Interface.

The feedback provided by the project coordinator was analysed, and new user requirements were identified. The low-fidelity prototype is currently being updated to a high-fidelity prototype, utilising the already established design system. Figure 30 shows an excerpt of the current design. The high-fidelity prototype is nearing completion and will then serve as a proposal to the EU-Commission responsible of the creation of the Green Deal Data Space and to the SAGE project.

Figure 32: Extract High-Fidelity Prototype (Version 3) - General User Interface.

4.2 AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES FOR FRONT-END IMPLEMENTATION

In the context of the AD4GD Pilot applications, the front-end implementation focuses on creating dashboards based on the clickable prototypes developed in Task 5.3. Open-source technologies, specifically Grafana and open.DASH, were closely considered due to the existing expertise within the project team. Grafana dashboards are already utilized by the AD4GD technical partners for system monitoring, while open.DASH is developed at Fraunhofer FIT. Each platform has unique advantages and disadvantages, making it essential to evaluate them according to the specific needs of the AD4GD project and the pilot applications.

As partially explained before, Grafana²⁵ is a well-known open-source platform for data visualization and monitoring. Its primary strengths include versatile visualization capabilities, allowing users to create various types of graphs, charts, tables, heatmaps, and geospatial maps. Additionally, Grafana supports extensive data source integration, connecting seamlessly with time-series databases and cloud platforms. This addresses the essential visualization requirements identified through the iterative Human-Centered Design approach used to create the clickable prototypes of Pilot 1 (SplashBoard) and Pilot 2 (BioConnect). Grafana also benefits from an active, supportive open-source community and a rich ecosystem of plugins. However, presents a steep learning curve, which can be particularly challenging for non-expert users.

Open.DASH²⁶ is an open-source dashboard creation tool that prioritizes simplicity and ease of use. Its focus on user-friendly, guided dashboard creation and adaption makes it accessible for non-expert users, enabling them to create dashboards with minimal effort. Open.DASH is lightweight and offers extensive customization options through the adaption of available widgets or the creation of custom widgets from scratch. However, as a newer tool, it has limitations in advanced features found in more established platforms. Its smaller community results in fewer resources and less support compared to Grafana. Additionally, open.DASH does not readily support as wide a range of data sources and integrations.

To isolate the implementation technology, a decision was made to utilize the same technology platform for both SplashBoard and BioConnect. This decision was taken due to two main factors: first, for human resource management and project scheduling, it was necessary to streamline efforts by adopting a single technology platform. Second, from a technical standpoint, there are significant similarities between the

²⁵ <https://grafana.com/oss/grafana/>

²⁶ <https://openinc.de/>

pilot applications in terms of features, such as central map navigation enriched with location data, metadata widgets, and upload functionality.

Furthermore, the features of both technologies were aligned with the requirements of end-users and insights from stakeholder engagements. This led to the conclusion that the functionality of the pilot applications could be developed using either Grafana or open.DASH. However, open.DASH was ultimately chosen for the front-end implementation for both pilot applications due to several reasons. The clickable prototypes will be transformed into functional applications by expert personnel at Fraunhofer FIT. However, end-users expressed a desire for the option to adapt existing dashboards and create new ones. For this purpose, the user-friendly approach of dashboard creation in open.DASH, with its rich dialogues and extensive widget catalogue, is more suitable. This approach can enhance end-user acceptance of the applications and support for deployed applications (even beyond the project's scope) becomes easier, as adjustments can be made by non-experts. Furthermore, the open.DASH visualization solution can be integrated with associated developments open.WARE and open.ANALYTICS to enhance dashboard functionality and increase flexibility in the front-end implementation, thereby realizing functional applications that closely align with the clickable prototypes defined with end-users.

4.3 FRONT-END IMPLEMENTATION

In Task 5.4 of the front-end implementation, we have selected open.DASH as the primary platform (see previous section), emphasizing a modular approach where each component is developed as a widget. This design choice enhances the stand-alone functionality of each component while offering flexibility in the user interface and facilitating the cross-usage of developments between pilot applications. The implementation task commenced with the SplashBoard tool, which has already undergone the entire Human Centered Design process and reached a Design Freeze. For the second application we are awaiting end-user feedback to the clickable prototype version 2 before reaching Design Freeze. The implementation of BioConnect will follow, benefiting from developments and insights gained during the SplashBoard implementation.

For SplashBoard, we initiated implementation of a header widget that serves as a centralized navigation tool. This widget features the AD4GD logo along with several essential functionalities aimed at enhancing user experience. For instance, there is an overview button that provides access to all water bodies, a favourite feature that allows users to display their preferred lakes for quick access, and an information button that offers additional insights into the AD4GD project. Moreover, we included a login button that facilitates user authentication, enabling access to personalized features, such as the ability to write notes about specific lakes in the future.

The landing page (see Figure 31) integrates a map of Berlin alongside a comprehensive list of all water bodies. This map displays all lakes and includes a search function that helps users efficiently locate specific lakes by name. On the right side of the page, users can find a detailed list that enables them to select a lake and navigate to its corresponding detail page.

Figure 33: The landing page with map and lake overview widget.

When a user selects a lake from this list, they are directed to the detail page, which features three primary widgets. One is the data Widget, designed to present general information about the selected lake, allowing users to mark it as a favorite, thus fostering a more personalized experience. The second widget is the Timeseries Graph, which displays various properties of the lake, such as water level and temperature over time. This functionality allows users to compare multiple properties across different timelines, offering the option to download the graph or associated data for their records. The third widget will enable users to leave comments on the lake details page; however, this functionality will only be available for authenticated users. The visibility of comments, whether general or specific entries, will also be tied to user authentication.

Currently, we have successfully implemented the header widget along with the landing page that contains both the map and the list of lakes. The detail page is nearing completion, with the integration and testing of both the data and timeseries graph widgets taking place. Our system architecture is designed to facilitate smooth data flow between sources (e.g., MinIO for lake time series data) and the open.DASH platform, ensuring that data handling is both efficient and user-friendly.

Figure 34: Lake Details page with Metadata and Timeseries widget.

Moving forward, our next steps involve further testing of the widgets to ensure their functionality and usability. We will also gather feedback from initial users to refine the overall user experience. This

structured approach will help us ensure that the final version effectively meets the objectives set forth for the AD4GD project.

5 SUPPORTING CONVERGENCE OF HPC, CLOUD, DATA AND AI

The Task T5.5 “Supporting convergence of high-performance computing, cloud, data and artificial intelligence resources for Earth system modeling” deals with the distribution of the workloads in the different building blocks of the GDDS. Each building block has some advantages compared to the other ones and this section explains how to handle the different kinds of data processing activities to be undertaken in the GDDS building blocks.

5.1 LINK WITH OTHER TASKS

First of all, this task is directly linked to the Task T2.5 “Ensuring data protection and compliance by design and by default”. Indeed, several elements in the Task T5.5 are common to the Task T2.5: firstly, the sharing of heterogeneous data among the different components of the GDDS architecture implies the utilisation of clear licences for the data owners and contributors. Secondly, an efficient data management, aligned with the current and upcoming European regulations, is of course required, based on the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles. The Task T2.5 brings the different possible solutions at the legal, organisational and technical levels to achieve the objective of protecting the different sorts of data.

The Task T5.5 is also directly linked to the Task T3.3 “Scalability and edge computing optimization”. The Task T3.3 consists of improving the scalability at the edge of the GDDS. It means to realise some computing activities linked to IoT devices directly at the edge and so, to avoid sending a large amount of heterogeneous IoT data to the cloud. The outcomes of the Task T3.3 can be used in the context of the Task T5.5.

Of course, the Task T5.5 is associated within the other tasks of the WP5, namely the Task T5.1 “AI and ML for data quality and uncertainty management and ground truthing”, and the Task T5.2 “AI, ML in HPC and cloud for data analytics and knowledge generation”. These tasks are already presented in this report.

5.2 DATA FLOW

The whole data flow currently put in place involves the heterogeneous IoT data generated by different kinds of sensors deployed at the edge in the different pilots. The cloud is composed by the FROST server which stores the IoT data sent from the edge. The HPC cluster enables the data processing activities done by the AI/ML components, notably on the IoT data available on the FROST server.

Figure 33 below displays the complete data flow between the different building blocks of the GDDS used in the context of the Task T5.5:

Figure 35: Data flow between GDDS building blocks.

The following sections explain in detail the different elements presented in Figure 33 above.

5.2.1 IoT/EDGE

Concerning the first part associated with the Internet of Things (IoT) and the edge, different steps are undertaken to ensure smooth transmissions of IoT data from the sensors to the FROST server. First of all, an initial data processing can be executed at the edge to initiate the collection of IoT data. This process requires that the dedicated IoT communication protocol is used not only by the concerned IoT devices, but

also by the edge. In this case, the edge has a supplementary role of IoT gateway or bridge for the given IoT communication protocol.

For instance, for the Berlin pilot, the IoT data is initially stored by the Berlin Wasserportal and published through CSV files; in this case, the Berlin Wasserportal hides the direct access to the IoT sensors deployed in the small lakes in Berlin. It means that the GDDS building block deployed at the edge has in fact several tasks to implement:

- Retrieve the CSV files using the API provided by the Berlin Wasserportal.
- Parse the content of the CSV files and convert it into JSON files compliant with the OGC SensorThings data model. This activity requires the use of the semantic interoperability developed in the AD4GD project.
- Send the IoT data to the FROST server through the OGC SensorThings API and the STApplus extension.

At the end of the day, the edge should simply ensure that the IoT data is fully aligned with the semantic interoperability defined in the project, and then, to convert them under the format used by the OGC SensorThings API.

An important requirement to be fulfilled by the edge is to reduce the amount of IoT data to be sent to the FROST server. Concretely, it means that the edge is able to handle all the processes to parse, convert and format all the IoT data before sending them to the FROST server. This point permits to reduce the necessary network bandwidth between the edge and the cloud.

5.2.2 CLOUD

The cloud is notably composed of the FROST server hosted and managed by IoT Lab. Its implementation is based on the FROST server developed by Fraunhofer, but encompasses new plugins to ensure the proper utilisation of the FAIR principles and the authentication mechanisms. The FROST server is responsible for storing the IoT data collected from the three pilots and then, to expose the IoT data through the OGC SensorThings and STApplus APIs.

The FROST server receives the data generated by the IoT sensors and forwarded by the edge, using the OGC SensorThings and STApplus APIs. The FROST server exposes the IoT data through the OGC SensorThings and STApplus APIs and so, it is possible from the HPC cluster to retrieve the desired IoT data for further analytics and other data processing.

To reduce the workload on the cloud and the necessary network bandwidth between the cloud and the edge, the concept of GDDS developed by the AD4GD consortium allows to compute the data already at the edge and to send only the results of any computation to the cloud. The amount of data transmitted from the edge to the cloud is decreased and only minimal work, such as data registration, is required at the cloud level.

For instance, the images captured by the trap cameras, which are in fact considered as IoT devices or sensors, are processed locally at the edge and only the results of the computation are sent to the FROST server. This reduces the required network bandwidth between the edge and the cloud. Furthermore, if the data generated from the camera traps, like the images, are handled locally at the edge, it decreases the risks linked to the exchange of potential personal or sensitive data between the GDDS building blocks located at the edge and the cloud. So, in terms of data protection and cybersecurity, it is a real plus to process the data at the nearest place of the data generation.

5.2.3 HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPUTING

A HPC cluster provided by PSNC was described in section 2.1 of the document in detail. A HPC cluster allows the implementation of a data warehouse which is not far away from the node concept in dataspace as described in the current European literature. Indeed, the data warehouse permits the integration of multiple sources of data in a common interoperable data model. Furthermore, it is possible to obtain a whole view of the complete data used inside the dataspace.

The utilisation of a HPC cluster in the context of the GDDS allows a continuous monitoring and optimisation of the use of the heterogeneous data. The high availability of a HPC cluster permits to reduce

the interruptions and to maintain a high reliability for the data collection and processing; this is particularly true and essential in the case of live and real-time data as expected by the AD4GD project.

5.3 SECURITY AND PRIVACY

As the data flow involves different GDDS building blocks, such as the different IoT sensors, the FROST server and the HPC cluster, the transmission of data, which could be potentially sensitive, requires a good level of security and protection. To achieve this goal, authentication and authorization mechanisms were studied in the context of the Task T5.5, too. Initial tests were done with Authenix²⁷ and the FROST server to validate the principles of the authentication applied to the IoT data stored in the FROST server. The access to the heterogeneous IoT data through the OGC SensorThings API now requires the authentication implemented through Authenix and the FROST server. Authenix is specifically dedicated to citizen science and research and allows accessing research data from different European projects and organisations. The FROST server was registered to the Authenix website and a specific access token can be now obtained from Authenix to access the AD4GD FROST server. Each transaction or request to the FROST server needs an access token delivered by Authenix. It ensures that unauthenticated or unauthorised users cannot access the datasets contained in the FROST server.

For the HPC infrastructure, it was decided to use Keycloak for all the GDDS building blocks when the data are exchanged through the data flow designed in the Task T5.5. Keycloak is well-known and adds authentication and authorisation in a quick way. Keycloak offers efficient user management as expected by the AD4GD project.

²⁷ <https://www.authenix.eu/>

6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the first half of this project, significant progress in the different areas integrating this work package has been made. Regarding the HPC usage, an infrastructure architecture based on the use of Kubernetes was proposed and implemented, also including a storage service based on S3, an industry standard nowadays in this particular aspect. This infrastructure is key for the rest of the processing made in the context of the AD4GD project, and the developments done in this matter are used along the tasks of most work packages. In particular, to take advantage of HPC in the context of AI, a set of tools was deployed to facilitate the experimentation, development and ulterior deployment of AI models that intend to assist pilots 1 and 2. These tools include Kubeflow, MLflow and Kserve. The available data was analysed and curated to be suitable to train the AI models specifically developed for pilot cases. And initial results on these models were presented, where further developments and improvements is expected to be presented in the next deliverable. Particularly, for pilot 1 we expect for the next deliverable to have results that indicate the influence of precipitations in their water level given artificial scenarios, such as intensive rains or droughts. Then, for pilot 2 better results in terms of output map quality are expected as a well as a performance comparison in processing time required to produce the outputs using AI as opposed to the actual pixelwise numerical computation.

In terms of user interface, after extensive studies on prototypes carefully designed in close relation with stakeholders to improve usability and effectiveness, the first implementation of user interfaces for each pilot was developed. For this purpose, we used open-source software, and after considering different alternatives Open-Dash was selected. In the remaining of the project further testing of widgets to ensure functionality and usability is expected, and improvements are also expected as a result of obtaining feedback from initial users that will translate into a better overall user experience. For the Splashboard interface, there is a need to include the functionality emerged from the AI modelling activity providing information regarding the impact of possible environmental scenarios, ultimately helping to prioritize actions on them.

The developments are well integrated with other tasks and activities in the project and with the IoT and edge platforms. Finally, the complete integration of the deliverable components of this project is expected to be completed and described by the time of the final deliverable 5.2.

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